

We thank the recommender and the three reviewers for those positive feedbacks and for their interesting comments and suggestions. We have responded (in italic and red) below point by point to all comments:

*The focus on the specific demographic scenario of Podarcis is seen as too narrow for a benchmarking study. Reviewers recommend either reducing the emphasis on Podarcis, or, including additional demographic models to increase the transferability of the findings across different species. The study focuses on fixed values for some parameters but reviewers suggest exploring/discussing how a range of parameters (e.g. divergence times, effective population sizes, number of individuals from the donor population, sample size...) could impact the detection of AI. This would make the findings more applicable to real-world datasets with varying parameters that are not too specific to the Podarcis system.

The previous version of our study was focused on the Podarcis scenario, characterized by its very early divergence times (>2 millions generations), which we had specifically chosen to strongly contrast the results previously illustrated by the authors of the methods, tested on a Human scenario (divergence time of ~20 000 generations). We have now followed reviewers' advice to test new factors, notably by considering two alternative demographic scenarios. The first scenario is inspired by human evolutionary history, and corresponds to the scenario used in the original articles of the methods tested, with notably recent divergence times. In this Human scenario, we also tested the effect of migration rate ($m \in \{10^{-3}, 10^{-2}, 10^{-3}\}$, small effective sizes ($N = 200$ vs. $10,000$), the presence of hotspots and sample sizes (30 individuals per population, vs $\{2, 2, 99, 108\}$ for SD, D, R and SR respectively). This Human scenario is now our reference scenario. We also include the previous simulations under the Podarcis scenario to assess the effect of divergence time and selection strength. Finally, to test the effect of the time of introgression, we drew on the evolutionary history of Brown and Polar Bears (introgression at 15,000 generations vs. $\leq 2,000$ for Human and Podarcis).

*A discussion on how various adaptive introgression models can impact the detection of AI could be interesting. For instance, adaptive introgression is often conceptualized as involving a single trait or locus, but hybridization can improve fitness in several additional ways (Edelman & Mallet, 2021).

Introgression could indeed have a complex effect on the fitness of the population as discussed by Edelman & Mallet, (2021). However, the methods we have assessed for the detection of AI have been designed to detect isolated loci in which an advantageous allele is introduced by introgression. Our test sets consider that target case with different levels of selection strength. We consider that discussing more complex cases of positive fitness effect on the introgressed population (e.g. alleviating genome wide mutation load) are beyond the scope of our work.

* The potential influence of selective sweeps on AI detection is not directly addressed. Reviewers recommend discussing how such regions could interfere with the identification of AI windows and impact the study's conclusions.

The possible impact of classical selective sweeps was evaluated by the authors of the four methods in the articles presenting them with results indicating that they are in general robust. We note this in the discussion (l.656-661).

-Comparison with other studies: In line with the comments above, including a summary table comparing the methods and findings of this study with those from previous research (e.g., Gower et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2023) would be helpful. This table could highlight key differences in simulated models, training approaches, and detection methods, providing readers with a clearer understanding of how this study contributes to the broader field of research on AI detection.

A table comparing the different scenarios used to train MaLAdapt and genomatnn and to test the methods in our study has been added to the supplementary information (Table S1). Summarizing all our results in a single table doesn't seem possible.

In addition, why not consider Ancestry_HMM-S (Svedberg et al., 2021)? Could the authors give a small explanation or benchmark of this approach?

We did not include Ancestry-HMM-S because this method requires certain parameters to be estimated before it can be used (migration time, introgression rate and effective population size). These parameter values are often unknown in non-model species and we wanted to use methods that did not require the use of other estimation methods for our study.

-Figure improvements: Merging Figures 2 to 4 into a single figure could improve readability by showing the differences in selective coefficients on one page. The ROC curves in Figures 2 to 4 could be moved to supplementary materials, while the ROC curves in Figure S4 could be moved to the main text for clarity. One reviewer also recommended incorporating the Matthews correlation coefficient and F1 scores when evaluating the different methods, especially in cases of imbalanced datasets.

These figures have become Figure 5, but we have added a separate figure (Figure 4) showing the method scores as a function of the distance from the windows to the AI mutation for the reference human scenario.

ROC curves representing the performance of the methods for the scenarios that led to the most interesting results have been added to the main text (Fig. 2 and 3).

Concerning the mccf1 curves, we are not convinced that adding these curves to the manuscript (which already has a large number of figures) would help the reader to better understand the results. Moreover, the results of the mccf1 curves are often in agreement with those of the AUCs of the ROCs. We found differences for three scenarios, the Podarcis scenario with weak selection, the bear scenario (except for the tests set with chromosome 2) and the human scenario with small population sizes. In these cases, mccf1 curves show that genomatnn performs better than the Q95 or MaLAdapt. These differences are due to the higher number of false positives for Q95 or MaLAdapt than for genomatnn in these scenarios, which corresponds to situations where all methods show poor performances.

Review by Thibault Leroy

Compared to the works of Gower et al. (2021) and Zhang et al. (2023), I noticed a key difference in objectives: the authors of this manuscript have focused solely on simulation work and have not extended their investigation to empirical data to identify candidate regions of introgression. Initially, I found this approach somewhat frustrating, as the authors have considered a highly specific demographic scenario corresponding to their species of interest (at least it seems so), and it would have found interesting to scan genomes of this species with the best method and/or observe the differences in detection among the different methods based on the real data. Given that the objective here was limited to the evaluation of the best methods based on simulations, the use of ranges of parameters (e.g. range of divergence time) rather than (more or less) arbitrary fixed values would have been better to ensure that the conclusions are not specific to the context used by the authors. I therefore encourage the authors to discuss the potential impacts of the choice made during the simulations in order to provide sufficient information for readers working on different biological systems (but see below). That being said, as the methods trying to detecting adaptive introgression are burgeoning, such a study aimed at benchmarking them represents a valuable contribution to the community.

Following the reviewers' advice, the current version of our work includes a variety of scenarios and several parameters are studied on a range of values to evaluate their impact on AI detection. This represents a major change in the focus of the work that makes its results more generic and globally addresses additional more specific comments.

From my perspective, genomic regions containing selective sweeps could impact the ability to detect windows associated with adaptive introgression. However, as far as I understand, this aspect was not included in the study (please correct me if I am wrong). How might such non-AI windows have impacted the detection of AI regions?

See answer to recommender above.

Regarding the figures, I suggest several improvements. First, Figures 2 to 4 could be merged into a single 1-page figure, showing low to high selective coefficients. Such an all-in-one figure would help visualize the differences and be overall more comprehensive. I was not convinced that adding the ROC curves (triangles) contributes the readability of the current figures 2 to 4. I think these ROC curves could go in a supplementary figure. Second, I think that the ROC curves shown in Figure S4 are however useful to summarize the beginning of the results section and I therefore suggest to move this supplementary figure to the main text.

See answer to recommender above regarding the merging and placing of figures.

We doubt the added value of removing the triangles representing the AUCs from the figures representing the scores as a function of the distances of the non-IA windows (e.g. Figure 4 and 5). It seems essential to us to represent this information on the graphs so that the reader clearly understands the link between the distributions of scores per window and the performance of the methods.

Even though I agree that direct comparisons of the results are difficult (lines 489-492), the manuscript could benefit from including a summary table providing information that allows the reader to compare the present study with those of Gower et al. (2021) and Zhang et al. (2023). Different columns containing information about the simulated models, training, differences in the methods, performance, etc., would be useful to highlight some of the differences discussed in the section from l. 476 to 499.

We have added a table (table S1) presenting the differences between the training scenarios of the simulation classification methods and our test scenarios. We have evaluated the possibility to include more information on that table, as suggested, but the result was cumbersome and not very helpful due to the discrepancies between scenarios, parameter values and evaluation approaches. A table does not seem to be the appropriate format for this comparison. The relevant results of those previous works are presented in the discussion in comparison with ours.

Minor comments:

l. 6 The paper by Mallet is not cited. Add "(2005)". These 10% vs. 25% values should still be considered with caution because of the limited number of groups/species considered by Mallet. There is still an open debate regarding the relative importance of hybridization in plants vs. animals (e.g., Monnet et al. 2023). Rather than indicating specific values, I think the most important is to emphasize that hybridization is a widespread phenomenon across the tree of life for sexually reproducing sister species.

Citation has been corrected. We believe the text already conveys the idea that hybridization is a widespread phenomenon.

l. 66: The authors argue that some parameters were kept similar to "facilitate comparisons to previous work focused on adaptive introgression in humans" (lines 183-184). That's why I remain a bit skeptical regarding the genetic nature of the results at some points. Based on what I understood, the main difference in the demographic scenario is the divergence time between the sister species, which involve a more ancient split (>1 Myr generation). From my perspective, such an older split would be more in line with most of the literature on secondary contacts and adaptive introgression. I would appreciate more information from the authors regarding the interest of this new model (e.g. arguing how deep the differences are in their model, providing a list of biological models for which this model could similarly apply, etc.) to help convince the reader that the authors have made a significant step forward to address the issue they have indicated regarding the human-only focus: "the behavior of these methods when faced with genomic datasets from evolutionary scenarios other than the human lineage remains unknown" (abstract, beginning of the introduction (l. 47-49), etc).

As answered above, the revised version of the manuscript considers a variety of scenarios: The human scenario is the reference one with recent divergence times between the donor and recipient species (~20,000 generations) and a recent migration time as well (~1,500g). The Podarcis scenarios allow us to observe the impact of an old divergence time (>2 million generations) but still with a recent migration time (~2,000g). Finally, the Bear scenario allows us to analyse the impact of an old migration time (~15,000g) but to keep a relatively recent divergence time (~ 50,000g). We consider that the combination of these three scenarios and the variation of some of the parameter values (migration rate, selection strength, etc.) make our results of general interest. In addition, the code to produce the evaluation is provided

(<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14181497>) and can be applied by the interested reader to another combination of parameters of interest to them.

l. 81: eight

Done

l. 99: Cite recent papers on *P. hispanicus* in this sentence to support the assertion that this species complex is becoming a model for the study of AI.

Given the major changes in the focus of our work after taking into account reviewers suggestions, this sentence was removed from the manuscript.

l. 143-145: use “when” rather than “where”

Done

l. 152 As far as I understand, the recombination rate is assumed to be constant along the genome in the simulations. Can deviations from this expectation impact the detection? Not sure if the focal species uses PRDM9, but still my question regarding the heterogeneity of recombination rates would remain valid in case of a loss of PRDM9.

We added two alternative human scenarios with 1kb hotspots placed on every 100kb window. In the first scenario one hotspot is in the window under AI at 20kb from the mutation under AI and in the second the hotspot is placed on the mutation under AI. The presence of hotspots seems to slightly decrease the performance of the methods, especially when one hotspot is on the mutation under AI.

l. 180: The reader should understand here: "As no information is available from the literature for *Podarcis*, we have considered the following parameters...." Remove "commonly accepted values," since there are no universally accepted values; these parameters are highly variable among species (N_e and m obviously, but also μ !). Bergeron et al. (2023) demonstrated how variable mutation rates are in reptiles. Here, by chance, the average for the species of reptiles included in Bergeron's study is similar to that observed in humans, but this value should not be considered as a “commonly accepted value”.

Done

l. 204-209: “extremely time consuming” (l. 201, l. 207, etc). This argument is often indicated in the main text, but could appear as a bit vague and/or weak. Would be better to explicitly indicate the computation time or its inflation (XX-fold increase in computational time) in order to allow the reader to evaluate the feasibility, and if so, the cost-benefit ratio of circumventing the problem by using the scaling factor.

It is clarified in the manuscript : “(i.e. over 100 times more than with the scaling factor, representing hundreds of thousands of CPU hours)” (l.215-216)

*To give an idea, we simulated 10 datasets in forward without a scaling factor for the *Podarcis* scenario with an intermediate selection force, computation time is 3775.6 mins per dataset, whereas with the scaling*

factor of 10, it took 18.5 mins per dataset. The addition of the scaling factor therefore reduces the forward simulation time by more than a factor of a hundred.

l. 273-276: Same comment than before. In addition, try to be as explicit as possible throughout the ms. Here, for instance, regarding the choice of not using Zns, the sentence indicates that this statistic was not used because it “does not carry pertinent information according to importance score”, which is a bit unclear/vague.

It is now clarified in the manuscript : “ZnS does not carry pertinent information according to the classification importance score of the extra-tree classifier algorithm of MaLAdapt”.

l. 351-352: Does this sentence really refer to Figs. S1-S3 ? From my perspective, it was more associated with Figs. S4 & S5. Please also double check that the supplementary figures are numbered in the order in which they are mentioned in the main text.

Figures and tables numbering was changed according to the order in which they are mentioned in the main text.

l. 364: I do not consider the current sentence to be particularly helpful. What is important are the values of the “certain distances”. I wonder if a summary table indicating these distances to reach a threshold value (e.g., AUC = 0.9, when reached) would be more meaningful for easier comparison of the different methods, rather than showing the AUC values on the Figs 2-4.

All AUC values in this study are specific to the settings chosen for each test and may not be taken as reference values. We thus think it is better to represent the variations of AUC to understand the trend of their relationship with the factors tested (and thus the qualitative effect of the factor) rather than giving threshold values. Moreover, showing all AUC values as we have done is the most complete way to report our results.

l. 365-367: I found this sentence particularly difficult to read. Please revise it.

The sentence: “Interestingly, this pattern of score decrease varies according to the methods and the strength of the selection changes the maximum AUC values reached by each method considered.” has been changed to : “Both score and AUC variation patterns varies depending on the methods considered[...].” (l.389-390)

l. 446-448 & l. 448, To make the comparison clearer, indicate: “AUC= 0.66 vs. 0.91, respectively”, “0.94 vs. 0.90, respectively”

We have kept “against” but we have added “respectively”.

l. 470: To be fully explicit, cite the original publication you are referring to.

Done

l. 471-473: rephrase

The sentence : "The Genomatnn and MaLAdapt simulation-based methods showed better performance than VolcanoFinder in our study and in previous evaluations, with MaLAdapt being better than Genomatnn with lower false positive rate and more robust results regarding hitchhiking (Zhang et al., 2023)." has been changed to : "In previous evaluations on scenarios departing from these characteristics, VolcanoFinder was also shown to perform poorly respect to the other methods Gower et al. (2021) and Zhang et al. (2023). " (l.593-595)

l. 496: FPRs

Done

l.505: Add a space between MaLAdapt & performs

Done

l. 512: sweeps

Done

Figs 2-4: indicate the number of simulations (200?) in the figure caption

Done

Review by Fernando Racimo

In this study, Romieu et al. perform an evaluation of different methods designed to detect windows of the genome that may have been subject to adaptive introgression (AI) in the past. The authors recognize that methods available are largely designed and trained with archaic human AI scenarios, and so look to test how well these methods perform in a different scenario, inspired by the demography of a complex of hybridizing species of the *Podarcis hispanicus* lizard species. I think the manuscript is well written, addresses an important question and provides information that might be useful to researchers interested in applying these tools to non-human genomes.

Major comments:

Given the careful construction of the demographic model and the fact the authors have been able to simultaneously implement all four methods in a typically non-human demography, I think the study would benefit from a slightly more generalized simulation assessment beyond *Podarcis*-specific demographic details. Do their results hold for cases where the donor and recipient populations are not as extremely diverged? Is the advantage of Q95 influenced by this strong divergence level of the *Podarcis* case? If so, at what point along the continuum of divergence on the way to human-Neanderthal would (perhaps) Q95 start under-performing relative to the other methods? This need not be an extensive assessment across multiple demographic parameters but even exploring a few parameter differences (divergence, admixture rate) relative to *Podarcis* would inform non-*Podarcis* studies in the future.

I'm (I guess, pleasantly?) surprised the Q95 seems to have better performance in these scenarios, above those of other more complex methods. I was particularly surprised given that MaLAdapt incorporates Q95 as a component statistic of the classification model (in addition to other AI-sensitive statistics). Yet, as the authors point out in the discussion, the under-performance of MaLAdapt and Genomatnn relative to Q95 may likely be due to the fact that the comparison uses pre-trained models for the ML methods that are tuned to the human rather than the *Podarcis* scenarios. How practically difficult or computationally costly would it be to generate *Podarcis*-specific training sets for these two methods? If this is too difficult for either model, then this difficulty or cost of generating training data should perhaps be elaborated in the Discussion, as a factor influencing the decision to use simpler summary statistics.

*First, we were unable to retrain MaLAdapt with new parameter values because the simulation scripts available cannot be easily modified to consider new simulation values, contrarily to genomatnn scripts that were relatively easy to adapt. Retraining MaLAdapt should be possible but with considerable efforts and interactions with the authors, so we consider it was out of the scope of the study. We were only able to retrain MaLAdapt by recycling the original MaLAdapt simulations with some statistics removed from the train set. We tried to launch new simulations with different parameter values but did not succeed to modify their scripts to do so. Second, we retrained genomatnn using the simulation pipeline provided by Gower et al., (2021). As in Gower et al., 2021, we used 300,000 training datasets in total (3 times 100,000 simulations with neutral introgression, with classical selective and with adaptive introgression). Under *Podarcis* historical scenario, this would take about 800 CPU days (given some preliminary simulation tests).*

Sample sizes used are equivalent to those used in the Genomatnn and MaLAdapt papers. These are specific to modern human and archaic human panels that were available to the authors at the time. I think a more general approach involving other sample sizes would make the paper particularly useful

to non-human, non-Podarcis researchers who want to apply AI methods to their study organisms (e.g. is Q95 still advantageous to use at smaller sizes, or larger sizes?)

We have added results for a human scenario with sample sizes different from those generally used for the human line, for which we had to re-train genomatnn. We chose sample sizes (n) that we could consider appropriate in studies of non-model species, n = 30 individuals per population, which means reducing the number of samples in the R (99) and RS (108) populations and increasing the number in the DS (2) population. The results are presented in the manuscript. A slight increase in performance of the order of 0.1% for the AUC can be observed for the Q95, MaLAdapt and VolcanoFinder, so it is difficult to conclude that the change in sample size had a real impact on performance with such small differences. The ranking does not change insofar as the best methods for this scenario are Q95 and MaLAdapt followed by genomatnn and VolcanoFinder. This slight improvement is due to the increase in sample sizes for the D and DS populations, which improve the power of summary statistics based on allelic frequencies.

ROC assessments may not be appropriate when datasets are imbalanced, and don't consider all four cells of the confusion matrix. In Gower et al., we used a combination of the Matthews correlation coefficient and the F1 scores (as recently recommended by Cao et al. 2020) as a way to account for these issues. It might be wise to use these statistics as well, when evaluating the different methods. See: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2006.11278>

We initially computed the MCCF1 scores and curves. However, we are not convinced that adding these curves to the manuscript would help the reader to better understand the results. Moreover, the results of the MCCF1 curves are often in agreement with those of the AUCs of the ROCs. As discussed above we only found differences for 3 scenarios.

Minor points:

I would bring some of the ROC curves from the supplementary materials into the main text, at least for a few scenarios (to me, they are easier to interpret than the AUC score plots). Alternatively, you could show F1-MCC curves, as suggested above.

Accordingly, ROC curves moved into the main text but we did not present MCCF1 curves as explained above

Line 27: another reason why it is challenging is that selection might occur on mutations that occur in the introgressed haplotypes after introgression (effectively driving the introgressed haplotype to high frequency even if there was not an advantage in the original non-mutant haplotype). See: <https://academic.oup.com/mbe/article/35/3/623/4705837>

Following reviewers' advice we have considered a large variety of scenarios in the new version of our work. However, in the interest of clarity and considering time investment, we had to choose among the new scenarios to include and this scenario was not considered in the new version.

Line 81: did you mean here "eight" instead of "height"?

Done

Line 101: "extant" -> "extent"

Done

In the supplementary material, there are several instances where it says "Podracis" instead of "Podarcis"

Done

Review by Lukas Metzger

In this study, the authors evaluate the performance of four different methods that were built as adaptive introgression (AI) detection tools. The efficiency of these methods is demonstrated through simulations of a demographic model which is inspired by the lizard species complex.

These new results provide interesting insights on the performance of these detection methods especially in non-model species, and the study will certainly be very useful to researchers wishing to know which method works best for their current dataset. The context of the study and the underlying method are nicely introduced, and the manuscript is well structured and generally easy to read. However, some influencing factors could be more clearly discussed or justified, and some general points could be phrased more clearly. These suggestions and other minor points are detailed below:

I have three comments on the impact of [1] different sample sizes on the detection of adaptive introgression (AI), [2] the rationale of focusing only on one demography (of the lizard species), and [3] the effect of population size/symmetrical gene flow on the detection of AI:

[1] How would sample size affect the detection of adaptive introgression? In your case, you have specific sample sizes of 99, 108, 2, and 2. However, this sounds like quite a large sample size for non-model species. How would detection be biased with much fewer samples? What would happen with more individuals from the sister donor population? Or what if researchers had samples only from two or three of these populations? I don't want the authors to change their model or simulations, but I would like to see a bit more of a realistic perspective on real-world data.

First, except for the outgroup that is only used to polarize the SNP polymorphism, the number of populations sampled and analyzed are constrained by the methods. The only method that can be used without the donor D (or sister donor DS) and the sister recipient RS population samples is VolcanoFinder. This is already stated in the manuscript (lines 60-63).

Sample sizes are indeed a potentially important factor and the sample sizes we used were strongly unbalanced and very large for the recipient and sister recipient populations. We have now tested the effect of sample sizes by adding a human scenario with more standard sample sizes for non-model organisms, i.e. balanced sample sizes of 30 individuals for all populations (i.e., we increased the donor sample sizes and decreased the recipients ones compared to the reference). Our results show only a small improvement with more balanced sample sizes except for genomatnn. We did not add more simulations to test the effect of independently changing the size of each population on performance as this would have required re-simulating training datasets and re-training genomatnn for each different size (which has already been done once for the case of balanced sample sizes).

[2] The introduction includes a section about the species (lizards of the genus *Podarcis*). I do not see this paper as a lizard adaptive introgression (AI) study, but rather as a strong benchmarking contribution about AI detection methods. I suggest removing that information or mentioning it much more briefly, as readers will be more interested in the general performance evaluation of the methods in non-model species than in the lizard species system. Why weren't more demographic models introduced to evaluate the performance of these methods? Making it a bit more general would be beneficial.

We have extensively modified the manuscript by greatly reducing the importance of Podarcis-inspired scenarios and adding a number of scenarios, inspired mainly by human evolutionary history and to a lesser extent by the brown and white bear history, to test different factors. We believe that the revised manuscript answers the above question.

[3] In many non-model systems, many different factors influence the detection of AI, which are not incorporated within the study. More complex scenarios are hardly discussed, but it would be interesting to at least discuss (or even incorporate into simulations) how these would influence correct detection (as is already explained for population structure). For instance, very small population sizes/bottlenecks, which are common in non-model species, or symmetrical/asymmetrical gene flow between the donor and recipient populations.

Simulation studies of method performances are indeed always limited by the number of factors tested that is virtually only limited by the scope chosen for the manuscript. We have thoroughly revised the manuscript, adding different scenarios to test the effect of divergence times, migration rate, introgression time, population sizes, sample sizes, and the presence of recombination hotspots, in addition to the influence of the strength of selection which had already been tested. The main limitation is the computation time of the simulations and the need to re-train certain methods (e.g. for different sample sizes).

Other minor points:

I am still not sure I understood the simulation process correctly. Are there regions within the 1Mb genome without introgression? As some methods use neutral introgressed regions as a baseline, how would the methods classify the windows other than the AI region in figure 2?

“Are there regions within the 1Mb genome without introgression?”

Yes, but where introgressions occur along the genome are random events. We simulated 2Mb genomes composed of two chromosomes of 1Mb (Lines 139-144). The first chromosome contains the AI mutation in its center and adjacent neutral regions. The second chromosome only contains neutral regions. Depending on each specific simulation trajectory, both the adjacent regions from Chromosome 1 and all regions from chromosome 2 potentially contain non-introgressed material. For the additional independent neutral introgression (NI) windows, all regions from the independently simulated 1Mb chromosome potentially contain non-introgressed material depending on the simulation trajectory (except at least one because we only rejected simulations without any introgression).

Thus in each simulated dataset, for training and testing, there is a chance that non-introgressed regions are present in the adjacent windows of chromosome 1, in chromosome 2 and in the NI chromosome, in proportions depending on simulation parameters.

“As some methods use neutral introgressed regions as a baseline, how would the methods classify the windows other than the AI region in figure 2?”

It is one of the main points of our study. We specifically considered three test sets (AI vs adjacent windows, AI vs chromosome 2 windows, AI vs NI) precisely to show the importance of taking into account different

types of non-AI windows when developing and training a classification method in order to avoid cases of misclassifications when these windows are not taken into account.

I like your introduction as it gives a detailed explanation about the rationale behind the study. However, I find that paragraph 105-119 does not fit perfectly in its current position. In the preceding paragraphs, you introduce the different AI detecting methods (l. 43-78) and the study species (l. 79-104), and then again in lines 105-119, you discuss about the AI detection methods. This information seems more fitting for the methods section or could be better placed after line 78. I understand you use this paragraph to transition into the aim section, but I believe it would be more fitting if it were closer to either the methods section or within the introduction where you initially introduce the current methods.

The introduction has largely been modified during the revision, notably these parts. We think that the sequence of methods and scenarios is now better structured, as suggested in the above comment.

It would be helpful to add labels on the x-axis of the plots, like "Distance from AI window" or something similar. Even though it is written in the caption, it would make the figure easier to understand at a glance.

Done

In line 6, you explain that "Mallet" estimated the amount of hybridization in animal and plant species, but you do not cite any of his papers in that specific sentence or the sentences before. It would be clearer to write "Mallet et al. (xxxx) estimated..." or a similar citation to ensure proper attribution and clarity.

Done, we added the citation of Mallet 2005.

Line 202: You mention scaling by 10, except for the m parameter. What was the reason for this? Wouldn't this bias the simulation? A short explanation behind this rationale would be helpful.

The explanation for this choice is given in the materials and methods section discussing the scale factor (Lines 212-218 in the model descriptions). We did not apply the scaling factor to the migration rate m , since both the original and the rescaled models are equivalent in terms of the proportion of migrants entering the R population.

Other minor corrections:

Line 79: Change "genetic dataset" to "genetic datasets".

Done

Lines 342 and 361: Correct "IA" to "AI".

Done lines 342, 361 and elsewhere.

The text needs some more typo fixing.

We corrected all typos highlighted by the reviewers and we did a complete proofreading, looking for typos.